

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Olimov Shohijahon Fozilxon-son

THE HUMAN FACTOR IS THE SIGNIFICANCE

DRJI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

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EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

